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Livelihoods and Tourism in Netarhat, Jharkhand: A Geographical Analysis

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ABSTRACT:

Netarhat, one of the famous tourist destinations in Jharkhand has been inhabited by many indigenous tribal populations. The quality of living in this tribal dominated region is still primitive in nature. Like the other tourist destinations in India, the livelihood of the residents of Netarhat is slowly changing. Though, modernization has started to affect their employment and income but it is not comparable to national or state level. The region has been suffering from poverty since distant past. Low level of literacy, agro-based economy, low income opportunities are responsible for their poor living condition. So, the main focus of this paper is to present a glimpse of livelihood conditions of Netarhat. About 25% of the families of the entire area have been randomly surveyed through personal interview and focus group discussions. The result which has come out from this survey is truly amazing such as the large concentration of dependent population, high rate of illiteracy, the dominance of primary activities a gro-based economy (subsistence agriculture) with low returns, poor housing condition and almost no household has any toilet facility. Therefore, it is necessary to bring them back to the main stream of modernization by making suitable measures otherwise they will gradually be deprived of different developmental and societal aspects. Therefore, this paper is being discussed about the livelihood characteristics of Netarhat.

KEYWORDS: Demography, Livelihood, Common Property Resource (CPR), Wasteland, Subsistence Agriculture.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Jharkhand, at the time of its formation, lagged behind the all India average in many of the key development indicators such as the economy, productivity, livelihood status etc. Afterward, it has made an impressive progress from the birth of the state i.e. 15th November 2000. However, different development programme have been reducing the gap but it still persists ¹. Netarhat is a popular hill station tourist place in Latehar district of the state of Jharkhand popularly referred to as the “Chotonagpur ki Rani” (Queen of Chotonagpur). Due to the advantage of elevation accompanied by temperate climate, Netarhat is developed as one of the leading fruit grown area in the state, especially in pear cultivation. Netarhat has the total population of 1497, of which 789 are males and 708 are females out of 266 households ².

A livelihood comprises the capabilities, assets and activities required for a means of living ³. Thus, the livelihood status is often discussed in a broad term as the satisfaction of human needs such as Drinking water, health, occupation and income, schooling etc ⁴. Therefore it is needed to increase the facilities, safety and security and other important infrastructure regarding the socio-economic activities in any community. Though the livelihood status is mainly primary activity based, Netarhat is designated as remarkable tourists spot under different tourism category of the state. According to the draft tourism policy 2014, it is a famous tourist spot. But, it becomes a place of politically turmoil and thus, it needs serious effort to improve from such of its current state ⁵. The study area is the homeland of many tribal populations and they are detached from many of the public facilities. Therefore, it is now the a crucial condition to develop with an improvement in living standards for the tribal population in which most of the population can participate in the process of socio-economic development ⁶. So, the livelihood development has emerged as a central component of any clan as well as tribes. The present paper is focused to illustrate the livelihoods snapshot of the study area.

2. OBJECTIVES:

The objective of the present study includes:

- To study the livelihoods including habitat, economy and the society of the inhabitants at Netarhat.
- To examine the degree of influence of tourism.

3. STUDY AREA:

Netarhat is a small village located under the jurisdiction of C.D block of Mahuadanr in Latehar district in the state of Jharkhand. It is situated at an elevation of 1,071 meters (3,514 ft) in the western part of the state. The socio-economic survey has been conducted at two different localities of

Netarhat village namely Paseripat (23°29'25.2"N, 84°15'16.8"E) and Mohanapat (23°28'46.7"N, 84°15'17.5"E).

Figure 1: Location Map of the Study area

4. MATERIALS & METHODS:

The household survey was conducted at the locality of Paseripat and Mohanapat of Netarhat village taken 67 households out of 266 households which is about 25% of the total household. The study has been conducted by collecting primary data using closed-ended structured questionnaire, open-ended questionnaire, and focus group discussion in the study area. For carrying out survey to get quantitative data, scheduled questionnaire was prepared. The tabulated data has been analyzed by using simple statistical methods. Discussions with elderly person, members of local Panchayat help in qualitative evaluation of the problems and future potentiality.

5. RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

The study on livelihood characteristics actually helps to understand the social, cultural, demographic and economic status of a particular region with its future prospects. The term livelihood characteristics refers to different conditions such as food habit, housing characteristic, demographic structure, lifestyle, religious status, amenities of life, education, marriage, apparel status, occupation etc of a distinguished settlement ⁴. The following livelihood characteristics are noticed in Netarhat village:

5.1. Demography:

Demographic characteristics of Paseripat and Mohanapat have been revealed after the analysis of surveyed data of 67 households of this locality. Table 1 shows the total 50.12% are male and 49.88% are female in this study area with a negative sex ratio of 1000: 995 which shows a quite positive situation with respect to sex composition in Indian rural localities. In the case of family composition, there are 79.1% households live in the joint family system, whereas 19.3% are of nuclear type family and 22.3% households have family members more than 10. It was noticed that Jharkhand state has always been a region of tribal concentration where the tribal population was sharing at around 36% of the total population of the state in the early 1950s, and around 27% by the beginning of the 1990s ⁷. The same scenario is reflecting in Netarhat where most of the households belong to ST category (94.3%) followed by SC (5.7%) category [figure: 2(a)]. In the study area, they speak in different tribal languages to communicate in their daily life such as Sadri (29.8%) followed by Oraon (23.9%), Santhali (13.4%), Briziya (9%), Kurukh (9%) etc. and only 14.9% of inhabitants of the locality prefer to speak in Hindi.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the study area

Variables		No. of Household	% of Household	Age- Sex structure (Years)	Male		Female	
Gender	Male	200	50.12		No.	%	No.	%
	Sex Ratio	Female	199	49.88	<10	34	8.52	36
				11-20	50	12.53	61	15.29
Caste	Male	1000		21-30	43	10.78	32	8.02
	Female	995		31-40	18	4.51	31	7.77
Language	ST	63	94.03	41-50	24	6.02	11	2.76
	SC	4	5.97	51-60	10	2.51	15	3.77
	Sadri	20	29.8	>60	21	5.26	13	3.26
	Oraon	16	23.9					
	Hindi	10	14.9					
	Santhali	9	13.4					
	Briziya	6	9.0					

Source: Compiled from the field survey

The age-sex pyramid [figure: 2(b)] of the study area shows almost similar characteristics of any developing country. About 8.5% of total populations are in the age group of below 10 years and 5.26% are in the old age group with above 60 years indicating the large concentration of dependent population. The age group of 11-30 years is composing 23.31% of the total population. It indicates the possibility of population explosion in near future.

5.2. Education:

Education is one of the main indicators of the development of human civilization. Education is considered to be the core key of a society which helps to learn or acquisition of knowledge, skills, and habits. It carries the content of human being also. Development of a region depends on the rate of literacy and quality of education of the population ⁸. The table 2 shows that educational status of the localities is poor. The literacy rate is quite below the national literacy rate of 74.04% in 2011.

Only 62.2% inhabitants are literate here and most of the educated persons are the first generation learner while the literacy rate of Jharkhand is 67%, a remarkable improvement from 54% ⁹. The percentage of literacy rate of male is 69% and for the female, it is 10% lower than male [figure: 3(a)]. The pattern of distribution of educational levels shows that 40.3% of them have completed their education at primary level followed by 33.46% in secondary level. Only 11.2% of the inhabitants attain higher education and 2.7% to the postgraduate level [figure: 3(b)]. Although a good number of educational institutions are being run in the State but the rural area still remains deprived of even primary education. Not only lack of teachers but also there is a serious lack of motivational force to read & write ¹⁰. Though Netarhat is famous for its top Residential school, it could not fulfill the demand of local inhabitants. For higher education, the learners of the area have to go to Latehar, Lohardaga, and Ranchi. About 78% of households are responded about the poor education facilities.

Table 2: Educational status of the study area

Levels	Male	%	Female	%	Literacy Status	Male	Female	Total
Primary	54	21.8	46	18.5	Literate	130 (69%)	118 (59.3%)	248 (62.2%)
Secondary	39	15.7	44	17.7	Illiterate	Male	Female	Total
Higher Secondary	12	4.8	07	2.8		70 (31%)	81 (40.7%)	151 (37.8%)
Graduate	13	5.2	15	6.0				
Post Graduate	05	2.0	02	0.7				
Others	07	2.8	04	1.6				

Source: Compiled from the field survey

5.3. Economy:

According to District census handbook 2011, Netarhat has a comparatively stable economic condition mainly primary in nature such as cultivators, agricultural labours, household industries etc. The inhabitants of Paseripat and Mohanapat are engaged in a variety of economic activities found mainly in the surrounding area. In the primary sector like cultivators, agricultural labours and related activities, about 73% of people are engaged followed by 27% in secondary activities [figure: 4(a)]. The higher engagement in primary activities results in poor household condition with average monthly income in between Rs. 4500-6000. About 58.3% households have the monthly income less than Rs. 5000 and only 5.95% households have monthly income greater than Rs. 20000. It has been noticed that higher the family member, greater the income in the study area. Table 3 shows it clearly and this is because every member of the family is associated with farming and joint farming system increases their income. Apart from this, the per capita wages is very low in the surveyed area. Majority of workers earn monthly income in the range between Rs. 2000-4000 [figure: 4(c)]. Only 4.2 % of workers have per capita income greater than Rs. 12000 per month. This suggests that the locality belongs to a low-income region of Latehar district as well as Jharkhand. Agricultural and related activities are the major source of income of the inhabitants. Though, the production of Rice

and Pulse are significantly increased in Jharkhand but the production of Wheat and Maize are declined sharply over the past few years ¹¹. In the study area, Paddy and corn are the two major agricultural products which are produced at a rate of 67.2% and 50.7% household respectively, followed by vegetables (14.9%), wheat (10.4%) and millet (8.9%). Irrigation facility is almost not available here, so prolonged period without rainfall or drought-like condition harms the agriculture and the local economy.

As Netarhat is a tourist spot, it is found that about 6.8% inhabitants are engaged in tourism based activities but these activities are mostly seasonal in nature depending on peak tourist flows during October to February in Netarhat ¹². The potentiality of the tourism based activities not only increases foreign and domestic income but also it creates employment opportunities, stimulates the growth of the tourism industry as well as triggers overall economic growth ¹³.

Table 3: Occupations and Income Structure of the study area

Variables		No. of Participants	%	Variables		No. of Household	% of Household
Occupations	Cultivation	86	58.11	Per capita Wages	Less than 2000	9	13.4
	Agricultural Labour	22	14.86		2000-4000	38	56.7
	Handicraft	8	5.41		4000-6000	10	14.9
	Manufacturing	16	10.81		6000-8000	4	6.0
	Business	7	4.73		8000-10000	1	1.5
	Transport	6	4.05		10000-12000	3	4.5
	Hotel	3	2.03		Above 12000	2	3.0
Work Participation	Male	113	76.35	Major Crops	Paddy	45	67.2
	Female	35	23.65		Corn	34	50.7
Monthly family Incomes (in Rs.)	Less than 5000	39	58.3		Wheat	7	10.4
	5000-10000	16	23.8		Millet	6	8.9
	10000-15000	5	7.5		Vegetables	10	14.9
	15000-20000	3	4.5		Fruits	4	6.0
	Above 20000	4	5.9				
Livestock Farming	Cow	53	79.1				
	Pig	16	23.0				
	Goat	24	35.8				
	Hen	17	25.4				

Source: Compiled from the field survey

5.4. Housing Characteristics:

The localities of Paseripat and Mohanapat have a quite uniform type of settlement. The unplanned arrangement of poor and very poor class families with narrow lanes is noticed at the first sight of localities. Generally, the houses are semi pucca and mud built with just one bricked house under survey. All of the houses are of one story out of 67 households surveyed, of which 32 have semi pucca and 35 have mud, stone and bamboo made houses. In semi pucca houses, floor is mainly made of mud. Tiles are widely used as roof material (94%). Strikingly, there are 68.7% of such houses made of the mud wall. Most of the families have double-room houses (34.2%) and about

17.6% of houses have more than 5 rooms due to their large family size. But, 94% of the households have no toilet facility and separate kitchen in the premises too. The individual household latrine program, a component of Swaccha Bharat Mission (SWM), has therefore faced several roadblocks and most of them are still prefer open field for a milieu of reasons ¹¹. Jharkhand Government is committed to ensuring that by the year of 2019, there will be 100% electrified household but up to 2018, it achieved only 57%, up from 47% in the past two years ¹. In the case of Netarhat, table 4 shows that there are 44.8% of households have electricity connection and only 26.9% of households have LPG connection with subsidy facility. Due to the abundance of natural vegetation and low population density, about 88% of households rely on fuel wood which is collect from nearby forest and village land as common property resource (CPR) and sometimes buy from the local market.

Table 4: Housing Characteristics of the study area

Variables		No. of family	% of Family	Variables		No. of family	% of Family
Nature of house	Mud	34	50.7	Availability of LPG	Yes	18	26.9
	Semi Pucca	32	47.8		No	49	73.1
	Pucca	1	1.5	Reason for not using LPG	High rate	7	10.45
Roof Materials	Asbestos	4	6.0		Risk	6	8.96
	Tiles	63	94.0		Availability of Fuel wood	36	53.73
Wall Materials	Brick	21	31.3	Electricity	Yes	30	44.78
	Mud	46	68.7		No	37	55.22
Floor	Mud	65	97.0	Toilet & separate kitchen	Yes	4	5.97
	Concrete	2	3.0		No	63	94.03
Source of Fuel wood	Forest	48	71.6				
	Village Tree	7	10.4				
	Market	4	6.0				

Source: Compiled from the field survey

5.5. Food Habit & Health:

Clean and safe drinking water and availability of sanitation are the fundamental rights of every citizen globally. The situation of public health is maintained by the facility of drinking water, waste disposal, sewerage system which is again guided by local authority and customs. The inhabitants of Netarhat collect their drinking water of essential necessity from tap (85%), followed by tube well and earth well [figure: 6(a)]. Only 6% of households have their own drinking water facility, others are dependent on the community tap. But the surprise is that the quality of water is satisfactory, only 29.9% of families use any kind of water purifying system. In the case of waste disposal, the management system is very unorganized or poor type. Inhabitants of these localities use personal dumping ground or left the garbage in the nearby wasteland.

The people of Netarhat have no excuse about their delicacy. They are especially vegetarian. They prefer to eat pork in different occasions and ritual ceremonies which are their pet pigs. In spite of a good income, they sustain their old eating habits and also use old cooking methods¹⁴. Thus, some nutritional improvement is required in their diet system. Table 5 expresses that Wheat (87%) and Rice (13%) are the main staple food in their daily menu. About 86.6% of households are dependent on Govt. hospital for medical treatment. But there is a lack of medical personnel and poor medicine supply is noticed in the health center and hospital. Health problems of any community are influenced by various factors including social, economic and political etc. and there is a proverb in circulation that the health status of the tribal people is very poor because of their isolation, remoteness and being largely unaffected by developmental processes¹⁵. Tribal dominant Netarhat has no exception in the same case. They are not well aware of their health and hygiene. As a result, the emergence of various insects driven diseases such as Malaria (50.57%), fever (68.81%), skin related diseases, gastro enteric diseases are the major threat to the inhabitants in the study area.

Table 5: Food habits and Health of the study area

Variables		No. of families	% of family	Variables		No. of families	% of family
Source of Drinking Water	Community Tube well	57	85.0	Staple Food	Wheat	58	87.0
	Tube well	4	6.0		Rice	9	13.0
	Well	2	3.0	Mode of Treatment	Allopathic	25	37.3
	Stream	4	6.0		Homeopathic	19	28.36
Water Treatment	Yes	6	8.9	Ayurvedic	23	34.33	
	No	61	91.1	Major Diseases	Malaria	34	50.57
Water purification system used	Boiling	15	22.4		Fever	26	38.81
	Filter	4	6.0		Skin	2	2.99
	Aqua guard	1	1.5		Others	5	7.46
	None	47	70.1				
Place of waste disposal	Personal	26	38.9				
	Wasteland	12	17.9				
	Anywhere	29	43.2				

Source: Source: Compiled from the field survey

5.6. Livelihood Characteristics:

In the study area, own community marriage is often very common among them. About 85.1% of families get their marriage in their own community but 14.9% families get their marriage in others community. The age of marriage for both male and female is same with respect to the country's constitutional law. In most of the cases, it was observed that the age of marriage lies in between 19-26 years for both male and female. Dowry system is almost not prevailing in this village (table: 6). 56.7% of households have following public media such as T.V (19.4%), Radio (11.9%) and use of the Internet (25.4%) but 43.3% households do not access [figure: 7] any public media. Motorcycle (14.81%), refrigerator, DTH facility are very uncommon in this village. However, bicycle (68.7%) is the main companion of daily transport in the study area.

Table 6: Livelihood Characteristics of the study area

	Variables	No. of household	% of household
Marriage	Own community	57	85.1
	Others community	10	14.9
Dowry System	Yes	13	19.4
	No	54	80.6
Transportation	Bi-cycle	46	68.7
	Motor cycle	21	31.3
Amenities	Television	13	19.4
	Radio	8	11.9
	Users of Internet	17	25.4
	No Access	29	43.3

Source: Source: Compiled from the field survey

Their main ritual ceremonies in Netarhat are Swarna puja, Diwali, Holi, Dushera and different folk dances include Paika, Karma, Nachni, Natua, Agni, Santhal, Sohrai, etc ¹⁶. However, modernization has been affecting their daily routine, culture and occupations. Therefore, their culture and occupations are now changing due to the effect of modernization and have also influenced their clothing section recently. At present, they have been adapted themselves to western dresses like trousers and shirts gradually to keep pace with the advanced civilization.

6. TOURISM IN NETARHAT:

Netarhat is one of the famous tourist destinations in Jharkhand. It is famous for its glorious sunrise and sunsets during summer months. The main places of tourist attraction in Netarhat are Magnolia Point, Upper and Lower Gaghrri Falls, Sadni Falls, Lodh Falls, Netarhat hills, Pine forest, Koyel View Point ¹⁷. Though majority of the working population are engaged in agriculture based economic activities (72.97%) in Netarhat but there are 6.08% inhabitants engaged in tourism based activities also (table 3). Engagement of local inhabitants in tourism sector of Netarhat is quite promising for the development of the region, although some outsiders are also employed in this tourism industry. Almost 86% of the tourist of Netarhat is mainly domestic and they are come from West Bengal, Bihar, Uttaranchal, Uttar Pradesh and Jharkhand itself. Netarhat shares 6.9% of domestic tourists from same state and same district and 3.68% of domestic tourists from same state but outside district in terms of tourism industry across the state ¹². The main season for tourism in this area is winter but tourists gather to see the waterfalls also in the rainy season. The main obstacle of tourism is that there is no local transport facility. Tourists have to rent a bus, car, gypsy from outside. As a result, the tourism market here has not been able to develop properly which is affecting the economy. There is considerable lack of hotel and restaurant for tourists to stay. Besides, there is almost no public toilet. Although, the number of tourists is increasing day by day, this is desirable in this region. So there is possibility of improvement in tourism industry in Netarhat in future

7. PROBLEMS OF THE STUDY AREA:

The overall perception of some civic amenities (table: 7) and problems have been detected in the survey village. The following are the major problems identified as follows:

- The transport network is very poor. Accessibility in terms of transport vehicle is also very less. Roads are very narrow to ply.
- As majority of inhabitants are involved in primary activities, so the unemployment problem is increasing gradually.
- About 38% of the people in the study area are illiterate, which has become the main obstacle to regional development.
- There are lacks of the primary health center. The medicinal supply is also very poor in hospitals and health centers.
- Most of the peoples are not aware of their constitutional rights and opportunities.

Table 7: Perception of Civic Amenities in the Study area

Types of Problems	Response (% of family)			Types of Problems	Response (% of family)		
	Good	Moderate	Bad		Good	Moderate	Bad
Education	8	38	21	Waste	2	33	32
Health	0	56	11	Roads	14	30	23
Electricity	4	30	33	Sanitation	4	15	48
Drinking water	7	38	22	Transportation	5	27	35
Price	2	50	15	Entertainment	2	38	27

Source: Source: Compiled from the field survey

8. SOME SUGGESTIVE MEASURES:

The area is confined to various socio-economic obstacles and hence it is deprived of many opportunities. Therefore, the overall development of the region is not possible without the help of Government and various organizations. The following proposals can attempt to improve their current status:

- Improvement in the tourism sector is needed with the improvement of transport networks (main key for the development of any community), hotel development and proper marketing for the scenic beauty of the Queen of Chotonagpur Plateau.
- Since most of the population in the study area is mainly dependent on agricultural activities, there is enormous scope to improve the land use of the study area by plantation and orchard development especially oranges, pear, flower etc.
- Refined water from natural waterfalls should be arranged from nearest point to provide pure drinking water facility.
- Efforts should be made to make them literate with improving educational facility.

- Jharkhand Govt. must be taken careful attention in an account to Policies implementation towards the understanding of the tribal communal system and the developments for the benefit of the tribes ¹⁸.
- The prevalence and effect of the diseases on the affected people decreases their working days which reduces their income and breaks the standard of living. So there is a need for a primary health center with active and experienced staffs.
- In such a low monthly income, it is very difficult to maintain their standard of living. The condition is worse when a natural phenomenon such as the emergence of drought occurs. So there is a need to secure their professions.
- An immediate measure should be taken to develop the civic facilities and beautification with cleanliness for future tourism and its related industrial development. The changing economy and social development by increasing income and employment should be the principal point because of the dramatic growth of the tourism industry over the last three decades ¹⁹.

9. CONCLUSION:

In the study area, it is noticed that some of the livelihood characteristics are tourism based and some of the characteristics are stagnant since a long past. The low monthly income and low per capita wages are one of the indicators of low level of economy of the study area. The mud wall and floor with tiled roof witnessed their nature-based lifestyle. The problems such as sanitation, poor medical facilities, lack of education, waste disposal, and unemployment have turned the area backward. Though Netarhat is famous for its Netarhat Residential School but apart from this, there is a lack of educational institutions in the surrounding area. The pattern of agriculture is subsistence in nature due to rugged terrain and very poor soil condition devoid of any irrigation. So it is obvious that other primary activities are not possible except tourism industry which helps to sustain their livelihood but it demands huge investment by the local authorities of Netarhat. As Netarhat is proud of Jharkhand, it is now essential to preserve the prestige and honour of the place. Modernization has now affected their lifestyle and customs in recent days. Therefore, it has become very essential to bring them back to the mainstream of civilization. Lastly, it is suggested that development of sustainable tourism with the involvement of local peoples, forest-based economic activities, an infrastructural development mainly trade and transport, electricity, and drinking water help to bring smile on the faces of the natives. Netarhat is also culturally very rich and if the right packaging will be provided by the state, it can be an attractive cultural tourist spot and in addition, the tribals can be more dignified if the tradition and livelihoods of them narrated by themselves with the help of local authorities of such region ²⁰. To accomplish this purpose, both the Government and Non-

Government Organizations (NGOs) should play the leading role to bring up Netarhat in harmony of development.

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6(a) 6(b)
Figure 6: Source of Drinking Water 6(a) & Major Diseases 6(b)

Figure 7: Basic Amenities Available

Figure 8: Perception of Civic Amenities